

A Look at the History of Darband

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One of the main tasks of historiography today is to cover the many thousand-year history of our people in an objective manner based on the ideas of national independence. The images of Zarautsoy, located in the oasis, were created based on the thinking and imagination of primitive people, while Darband is considered to be the priceless abode of our ancestors who lived in a settled manner. The initial urban planning culture formed in Zharkoton is a prelude to the processes of urbanization development in our country. The early days of Uzbek statehood are closely related to the ancient Bactrian regions that settled on this land. The oasis was a shield even in the times when the enemy attacked the territory of our country from the south. The oasis has a significant contribution to the formation of the spiritual and spiritual values of Zoroastrian religion based on high philosophical and ethical beliefs. Considered one of the world's great conquerors, Alexander of Macedonia admired the courage and bravery of the people. During the Seleucids and Greek-Bactrian kingdoms, the local culture of the people of the oasis merged with the ancient Hellenic culture, and even the development of the powerful Kushan kingdom, which influenced it, is directly related to this blessed land. The people of the oasis played an important role in the history of our country and also in the history of the peoples of the East even in the middle ages. In the development of all states formed in the region during the Middle Ages, this ancient place has a worthy place. Even the founder Amir Temur received the flag and drum, which are considered symbols of statehood, from the piri Sayyid Baraka in the village of Biyo near Termiz. During the Middle Ages, many scholars who lived in the oasis contributed their fair share to the development of religious and worldly knowledge. In the development of the Islamic religion, which has enriched the spiritual treasure of mankind, the people of the world have a great role. Darband is a village belonging to Boysun district of Surkhandarya region. The inhabitants of the village are mainly engaged in animal husbandry, farming and horticulture. There are three gorges in Darband, they are called Darband gorge, Darband mine, and the third one is called Buzruk dara, which means the great gorge. The word Darband is derived from Persian, "dar" - "door", "gorge"; "band" means "strong", "strong", "obstacle". The village has several hundred years of history and has served as a transit station since ancient times. During the period of the Bukhara Emirate, the road passing through the village was considered the closest road connecting the western part of the emirate with the eastern part. After the railway was laid in Termiz in 1929, the road through the village lost its importance. But even today, this road is one of the roads connecting Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya. The social way of life of the people in the Surkhan oasis in ancient times, the tools they used, their religious ideas, and the places and monuments where ancient people lived in the oasis. Early stages of history and its historical significance. Stone sources, texts, inscriptions, various images, paintings, and at the same time the first samples of stone tools of the Stone Age, which is the first stage of human society, are the result of human creativity. People dedicated the wonders of nature and its mysteries to living creatures, created their images. By drawing pictures, they tried to exert their influence on things and events in nature or subjugate the natural conditions in it. The first people, who were formed under the influence of these imaginations and began to collect their first primitive experiences, used natural ready-made caves and rocks to draw pictures of the miraculous works of nature. One of such settlements is Zarautsoy, which is a rare example of primitive art carved on ungar and belt stones in a gorge located on the slopes of Kohitang mountain in the southwest of the Hisar mountain range of the territory of Uzbekistan. It is a place of culture. As a result of the archaeological excavations carried out in Sherabad, Shorchi, Bandikhon districts, clan community spaces were found in monuments such as Sopollitepa, Mo'lali, Jarqo'ton. The Sopollitepa culture

was formed in South Uzbekistan and was the first place based on artificial irrigation. Paleontologists found here the remains of agricultural wheat, barley, oats, cotton seeds, pottery, the use of the wheel, handicrafts. found the remains of artifacts and art samples. Most importantly, the fortress built to protect the tribe from external enemy attacks is surrounded by a three-line defensive wall. The total area of the fortress is about one hectare, and in the houses where eight communities lived, a fireplace with a chimney, a sandal place, and many plaster remains were found in some rooms. More than 20 pottery khumdons, high-quality elegant cups, jugs, khums, teapots, plates, defensive weapons, dishes, mirrors, textiles, thread and silk fabric remnants were found and studied. Our ancestors who lived in Sopollitepa were in close contact with the neighboring peoples as early as the Bronze Age. In particular, many objects found here are very similar to objects found in South Turkmenistan. Mil. avv. Between the 18th and 15th centuries, there was a lively life in the settlement of Sopollitepa, but avv. In the 15th century, due to the drying up of the waters of Ulanbuloksoy, the people of Sopollitepa left this settlement and moved to the banks of Bostonsoy, which is considered an ancient tributary of the Sherabad river, and here they established the first urban culture known and famous as Jarqo'ton. those who formed

List of references

1. Isayev, Oybek. "THE ORGANIZATION OF A ZOO IN THE CITY OF TERMIZ, SOUTHERN REGION OF UZBEKISTAN." Interpretation and researches (2024).
2. Isayev, Oybek. "THE CULTURAL LIFE IN SURKHAN OASIS: INFORMING OF ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROBLEMS BASED ON ARCHIVAL MATERIALS (1925–1941 YEARS)." *The Light of Islam* 2019.4 (2019): 31.
3. Qudratov, Namoz, and Oybek Isayev. "DENOVO BOZORI FAOLIYATI 1946-1961-YILLAR." *Talqin va tadqiqotlar* (2024).
4. Oybek, PhD Isaev. "In the Study of the History of Surkhandarya in the 30s of the XX Century, as a Historical Source." *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics* 7 (2022): 100-102.
5. Исаев, Ойбек Ахмед. "Освещение проблем образования Сурханского оазиса в архивных материалах (1920-1930 гг.)." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 6.8 (2020): 289-294.
6. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastrian Religion." *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
7. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИДА ДАФН МАРОСИМЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ." *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH* 3 (2023): 201-208.
8. Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "THE ROLE OF ANCIENT BACTERIA AND MARGIA IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ZARDUSTIYA." *Chief Editor* 12.
9. Бабаева, Ситора Рuzимахматовна. "Взгляд на историю топливно-энергетического комплекса Сурханского оазиса." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 7.2 (2021): 394-397.
10. Boboeva, Sitora Ruzimahmatovna. "HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE FUEL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN." *World Economics and Finance Bulletin* 4 (2021): 6-8.
11. Бобоева, С. Р. "Исторические топонимы вдоль торгового пути Термез-«Железные ворота»." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 6.2 (2020): 347-355.
12. Бобоева, Ситора. "БОЙСУН ТАРИХИЙ ТОПОНИМИ ҲАҚИДА." *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ* 21 (2019).
13. Sitora Ruzimakhmatova Boboeva. (2023). THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTRIC NETWORKS IN THE SURKHAN OASIS. (USING THE EXAMPLE OF 1914-1941). *Scientific Impulse*, 2(13), 300–306.